

Business intention of students with family business and entrepreneurial education background

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to examine the effect of family business background and entrepreneurial education background on the business intention of the fourth-year students. To deepen the understanding of the topic and to establish the theories of the study, literature was reviewed. It used a descriptive correlational research design. The population of the study was the fourth-year students and total enumeration was applied. The results of the study indicate that family business and entrepreneurial education background are correlated significantly with the business intention of the students. It further found that students who have a family business background and entrepreneurial education background have higher business intention compared to those who have no both.

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Introduction

Full human welfare and human development are dreams of everyone but to achieve these dreams, everyone has to contribute. Relying solely on the government to provide everything that human needs without the participation of all its citizens may be impossible. Depending on the government to develop full human potential can also be impossible. The government relies on its limitation in fulfilling its obligation to serve the needs of all its citizens specifically during and maybe after the pandemic and therefore, the government invites foreign and domestic investors to invest in the Philippines (Department of Foreign Affairs, 2020). The invitation is extended to the local investor to find business opportunities and invest (Department of the Interior and Local Government, 2020) and at the same time, DILG advises local government units to strengthen their capabilities to improve the local economy and provide conditions to attract investment. Recognizing the crucial importance of private individual contribution to economic development, the Government has established a Public-Private Partnership Center or PPP in the Philippines. Its objective is to improve efficiency and project implementation processes in providing services to the public (Public-Private Partnership Center, 2020).

Individual citizens' participation in the economy is recognizable in the Philippines and the world through the growing numbers of family businesses as pointed out by Go (2018). In his report, Go (2018) recognize that in the Philippines, 80 per cent of businesses are owned by families and in Southeast Asia, 65 % of businesses are owned by families and according to the estimate of Family Owned Business Institute (2020), that 70-90 per cent of the world's GDP is contributed by the family business. An estimate of 85 per cent of worldwide business is owned by families (Family Owned Business Institute, 2020). According to Baron (2016), the 21st Century will belong to the family business because of its capability in adapting its management to a competitive environment and

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because of its strong family values. These reports indicate that human welfare and human development are not just the government efforts alone but it is contributed much by the participation of private individuals or families.

It is undeniable that students of private education come from diverse occupations. Some may come from families that own a business, some may come from families that are working with the government or some may come from families that are simply working with another business establishment. American Psychological Association (2017) pointed out that different socioeconomic background affects overall human functioning which includes physical and mental health. It also affects the academic performance of students (Thomson, 2018, Okioga, 2013, O Kelly, 2019) and their academic interests. Morgan, Farkas, Hillemeier, and Maczuga, (2009) in their study found that students who come from low socioeconomic backgrounds developed slower academic skills compared to students who come from high socioeconomic status. In short, these studies pointed out that family background and their exposure to a family socioeconomic situation affects their choices and academic achievement. Family business exposure means students have been in contact with the business of their families or have been introduced to the business of their families.

Though it is recognized that socioeconomic background and their exposure to the family business may affect business intention, however, it cannot also be denied that education plays a role in changing the mindset of students and this is the purpose of education (Kazakoff & Mitchell, 2017). This is also the purpose of entrepreneurial education. Entrepreneurial education is intended for all students coming from socio-economic backgrounds. The purpose of entrepreneurial education is to prepare students to be entrepreneurs. It is expected that the output of entrepreneurial education is to change the mindset of students to think outside the box. In other words, the output of entrepreneurial education is creative thinkers, innovators, and risk-takers (Knowledge Review, 2021).

There have been studies on the relationship between family business exposure and entrepreneurial education and business intention such as the study of Zman, et.al., (2020), Ayuni (2018), Ndofirepi (2020), Wang, et.al.(2018), Lingappa, et.al (2020), and Swanepoel & Malebana, (2014). However, there have been no studies yet found on the difference between the business intention of students who have a family business and entrepreneurial education and those who have no family business exposure and entrepreneurial education. This is the main focus of the current study. The finding of the study will help the school administrators with the emphasis on curriculum development and to improve the teaching strategy of entrepreneurial education. The result of the study is expected to enrich the discussion on the content of entrepreneurial education and the importance of exposing students to the field of business while taking up entrepreneurship education courses.

The study is divided into five parts. The first part is the introduction or the rationale of the study which explains the reason why the study is conducted. The second part is the literature review that explains the theoretical foundation of the study. The third part is the research methodology. It includes the research design, the population of the study, the locale of the study, the research instrument, research procedures or data administration, and statistical treatment of data. Fourth is the empirical data presentation and analysis which presents the data gathered through research instruments and interprets the data. The fifth is the result and discussion and conclusion.

Literature Review

The literature review is an investigation of existing knowledge that has been published earlier by other researchers. This is to inform the readers on what knowledge or ideas have been established along with the current research topic and identify what their strengths and weaknesses are. This is to identify the gaps that exist between previous studies and the current study. It also helps to identify and explain the theories of the study (Taylor, & Procter, 2020). Along with such a concept, this part presents the existing discussions on the current topic and based on those discussions, the theories of the current study.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

The Concept of family Business and Students' Business Exposure

The family has been playing important role in supporting the economic growth of a certain country. Go (2018) in his report has pointed out that 80 % of businesses in the Philippines is controlled and owned by the family and in fact, it is known that family-run business still dominates the Philippine business (Francia, 2017, Remo, 2018), and in South East Asia, 65 % of businesses are controlled by the family. Family Owned Business Institute (2020) also estimated 70-90 of the world's GDP is contributed by family businesses. These statistics indicate that many families in the Philippines, South East Asia, and the world are engaged in the family business. In other words, family businesses serve as drivers for economic growth (Dieleman, 2018). The concept of the family business has been varied from one researcher to another researcher. Collins (2012), contends that family business means a family owns a majority share of the company and it can influence the direction of the company through its decision-making power. It influences the election of its Board of Directors. Similar to this definition is offered by Rosenblatt, et.al. (1985). Rosenblatt, et.al. (1985) define family business in terms of ownership, that at least two of the family members are involving themselves in the management of the business. Leah (2011) defines family in terms of ownership, that it is considered family business when the family owns a share of greater than 50% and a majority of its management are family members. While Davis and Stern (1980) see family business from its decision-making power. It is considered a family business when policies and decisions are influenced by family members. In this regard, the family has family members who are participating in the management of the business. Thus, in summary, Shankar and Astrachan (1996) offered several criteria to consider to be a family business such as percentage of ownership, voting

control, power over the strategic decision, the involvement of multiple generations, and active participation of family members in the management.

There are many types of businesses such as service business, merchandising business, and manufacturing business. Families may either engage in one or other two these types of business and sometimes some families engage in hybrid business which involves more than one type of business (Accounting Verse, 2020). In terms of forms and ownership, a family business may include a sole proprietorship which is owned by one person or family. This form of business is usually dominated by small family businesses. Some families engage in partnerships in which more than two persons or families contribute resources to form a business. Many more forms of business that family may involve in such as a corporation, limited liability Company, cooperative and non-profit organization. Related to the types of business, Dieleman (2018) identified four types of business in Asia in terms of complexities. First is a simple business, a simple family that focuses on one particular service and is managed by a few family members, not all siblings are involved. Second is a simple business, a complex family that focuses on a single service but many family members get involved in the management and get a share of the business wealth. The third is a complex business, a simple family. This type of business has small family owners but has diversified business forms. The fourth type is a complex business and complex families which involves many forms of businesses and many family members are involved in the business operations and get the share of the wealth of the business.

The Philippines has classified businesses into micro, small, medium, and large business based on the asset size. Based on The Magna Carta for MSMEs, 1991, a business that has an asset size up to 3000,000 is considered a micro business, from 3000,001-15,000,000 is considered small, from 15,000,001-100,000,000 is considered medium and lastly beyond 100,000,000 is considered large business (Tibaldo, 2019). Based on DTI's (2016) report, 851,756, or 89.94% of businesses are considered micro-businesses, 87,283 or 9.22% are considered a small business, 3,886 or 0.41% are considered medium and lastly, 4,063 or 0.43% are considered a large business. In terms of employment distribution, the micro-business contributes 30.46% of employment, the small business contributes 25.51% of employment, the medium contributes 6.83% of employment, and 37.20% are contributed by large businesses. In short, the majority of employment in the Philippines are contributed by micro, small and medium enterprises. These businesses may include different kinds of businesses such as accommodation and food services, agriculture, forestry and fishing, arts, entertainment and recreation, construction, education, electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply, financial and insurance activities, human health, and social workers activities, information and communication, manufacturing, mining and quarrying, other service activities, professional, scientific and technical activities, real estate activities, transportation and storage, water supply, sewerage, waste management and remediation activities, wholesale and retail trade: repair of motor vehicles and motorcycle (Philippines Statistic Authority, 2021).

From the classification of different kinds of business that have been pointed out and though there are no statistics to indicate the number of parents of students who own business, it is quite sure to assume that there are many students in the private catholic education come from a family who owns the business. Private schools are known to be expensive in the Philippine context and only those who can afford them can enter the private Catholic education. The family who owns a business may expose their children to the business. Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura, 1986) would argue that knowledge and intention are a product social environment. By observing the social environment such as parents, friends, peers, or entrepreneurs, one forms an idea of cognitive attitude, and behaviours (Ajzen, 1985). Exposure to the environment may affect the behavioural intention of students to be an entrepreneur. Zaman, et.al. (2020) pointed out the effect of individual exposure to the family business on the business intention of the person. Their study revealed that exposure to the family business affects the individual intention to do business in the future. A similar finding was also presented by the study of Tarling, et.al., (2016) that early exposure to the family business and its values motivate or influence someone to go into business. It is further confirmed by the study of Georgescu and Herman (2020) that students who have family business backgrounds affect their intention to go into business in the future. However, the study of Ayuni (2018) contended that actual entrepreneurs are the product of exposure to family business and education. In other words, exposure alone is not enough without entrepreneurial education (Georgescu & Herman, 2020).

Entrepreneurial Education

Entrepreneurial education has been spreading in all educational institutions around the globe since it was started by Harvard University in 1945 (Linan, 2004). The purpose of entrepreneurial education is to produce entrepreneurs. It is expected that after students learn the theories and skills about a business apply them by establishing a business (Li & Wu, 2019). However, studies have shown that not all college students who have taken entrepreneurship education have established a business or become an entrepreneur (Shen, Chen, & Chen, 2010). What is wrong? This is the beginning of research to identify factors that contribute to the influence toward the business intention of the students and this is also the reason why researchers have changed their focus of research. Instead of investigating entrepreneurial education and business intention, they investigate personality traits (Nelson, 1977), demographic variables such as gender, age, educational background (Barnire, Watson & Hutchins, 2011; Martin, McNally & Kay, 2013), and cognitive theory (Donellon, Ollila & Middleton, 2014; Nanda & Sorensen, 2010; Sivarajah & Achchuthan, 2013). The concern of research is then not only to find out the effect of entrepreneurial education and business intention of students but also to include other social factors that influence business intention.

It cannot be denied that entrepreneurial education is important but the issue of the objective of entrepreneurial education has been raised. What is the purpose of entrepreneurial education? There are conflicting ideas along with this concern. Wie, et.al (2019) argued that the purpose of entrepreneurial education is to transform the mindset into an innovative mindset. An innovative mindset is considered an entrepreneurial mindset and is considered as an internal driver of an entrepreneur, therefore entrepreneurial education must focus on the strategy of how to develop or cultivate the innovative ability of the students. In this regard, entrepreneurial education should be able to teach the students how to identify market opportunities and develop new products ((Miller, 1983; Covin and Slevin, 1989, Arthurs & Busenitz, 2006; Kettunen et al., 2013). This is what Lackeus (2015) argued that entrepreneurial education should be oriented toward value creation. Therefore, the content, method, and activities of entrepreneurial education must develop knowledge, competencies, and experience to help to prepare students to identify opportunities and create value for customers, shareholders, society, employees, etc, (Moberg, et.al., 2012, Lackeus, 2015). Teaching strategies then should support the value creation and therefore learning which is confined in the classroom is not enough without practising it. Thus, the appropriate teaching strategy is learning by doing of John Dewey or learning by creating value (Lackeus, 2015).

Besides an innovative mindset, another purpose of entrepreneurial education is to foster a creative mindset of students to support an innovative mindset (Binks, et.al. 2006; Gunday, et.al. 2014). To gain such a mindset, students need to be exposed to the different business environments, organizations, and entrepreneurs (Anderson, et.al. 2014). Exposure to a different environment will help the student to acquire adaptive behaviour (Ferris, et.al. 2005; Tocher, et.al. 2012). To emphasize the point, Constantine (2017) argued that an innovative and creative mindset is the tool that one can use to survive in a volatile environment and according to him, it is the main objective of entrepreneurial education. It should help the students to be the originator or creator of ideas and to be able to think outside the box. Besides an innovative and creative mindset, Constantine (2017) also contends that a risk-taking mindset is also another quality that is needed to be a successful entrepreneur. Those are the qualities that the learners should possess after acquiring entrepreneurial education so that they may survive in the world of business (Uleanya & Gamede, 2017). Thus, it is not only the concept and technical skills that are needed to survive in the world of business competition but even the mindset or attitude (mental awareness) that help to survive in the business (Erasmus, et.al. 2006). Constantine (2017) also pointed out that besides cultivating the entrepreneurial mindset, entrepreneurial education is oriented toward providing skills and knowledge about business to guide the students on how to establish a business.

In summary, entrepreneurial education is oriented toward creating knowledge, skills, mindset, competencies, experiences, and value creation. The end of entrepreneurial education is creating a business to create values for customers, society, shareholders, individuals, family, parents, etc.

Business Intention

Cambridge Dictionary defines intention as "something that you want and plan to do". A similar definition is offered by Merriam Webster. It defines intention as "what one intends to do or bring about" or "a determination to act in a certain way". From these definitions, it shows that intention is a plan to behave in a certain way. Logically, the intention will lead to a certain action. In this regard, intention serves as a motivational factor to perform a certain behaviour, and therefore, the stronger the intention is, the more likely the intention will be performed (LaMorte, 2019). Following such a line of thought, therefore, the intention is a planned behaviour (1991). This theory assumes that behaviours are pre-planned, a well-formulated action in advance. Before individuals perform a certain behaviour, they evaluate all available information about a behaviour they are going to perform and they can only perform after the evaluation of the behaviour. The action will be dependent on the result of the evaluation if it is good or not in front of the significant others and if they can perform such action or not or if it is within his control (Ryan, 2010).

The intention is influenced by different factors. Lean, et.al. (2009) identified several factors that affect the intention such as trust, perceived usefulness, perceived relative advantage, and perceived image. Besides these factors, there are other factors identified by different researchers such as easiness (Kang, 2014), positive attitude or degree of favorableness (Taib, et.al., 2008), attitude and subjective norms such as important others (McCarthy, et.al., 2003), perceived barriers, benefits, susceptibility, optimism and pessimism (Bunn, 2002), ethical belief, product safety, health, price and availability (Kavaliauske & Ubartaite, 2014), control, inclusion and affection (Jingsong, et.al.2012), the absence of fear (Leon, et.al. 2016, 358-367), beliefs related to the community benefits(Proudlove, et.al., 2020), attitude, trust, perceived usefulness, perceives ease of use and perceived behavioural control (Omatayo & Adebayo, 2015), perceived barriers (Hsieh, 2016), attitude, perceived behavioural control, awareness, and knowledge (Terano, et.al., 2015).

Concerning business intention, several studies have identified factors that influence the intention of students to go into business. Researchers have identified factors that arouse the intention to go into business such as attraction, networking support, entrepreneurial capabilities, self-independence and self-reliance (Hunjra, et.al. 2011), personal qualities, image of student entrepreneurship and environmental impact (Zivile, et.al., 2018), creativity (Agbim, et.al., 2013), entrepreneurship education, personal traits (locus of control and innovativeness), subjective norms, perceived behavioural control, gender and entrepreneurial experience (Xu, et.al., 2016), organizational factors (unfavourable innovation climate, lack of technical excellence incentive), self-efficacy (lena, et.al., (2009), need for achievement, subjective norms, economic situations, and entrepreneurial education (Joseph, 2017), entrepreneurial education (Paco, et.al., 2015), entrepreneurship curriculum, role and demographic variables (Anas & Ahmed, 2017), personal attractiveness, social norms and feasibility (Krueger, 2000), desire for success and challenge, attitude toward entrepreneurship,

perceived behavioural control, experience with entrepreneurship, and creativity (Tuan, et.al., 2019), the influence of family members, academics and attending courses on entrepreneurship (Zain, et.al., 2010) and personality traits, socialization and education (Nga & Shamuganathan, 2010).

Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework is a diagram that reflects the correlations between variables (Cueva, 2010). It is based on the literature that forms the theories or the key concepts of the study or variables (Creately, 2020). The current study reflects the correlation between independent variables and dependent variables. It reflects the cause and effect relationship which means that when independent variables change, it will affect the dependent variables (Thomas, 2020). On the left side, the independent variables are family business, and entrepreneurial education, while on the right side is the dependent variable which is business intention. It shows that family business exposure and entrepreneurial education affects business intention.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework; *Source:* Zaman, et.al. (2020), Tshikovhi and Shambare (2015), Abun, et.al.(2018)

Statement of the Problems

The purpose of the study is to determine the relationship between the independent variables and dependent variables particularly family business exposure, entrepreneurial education, and business intention. The investigation is guided by the following questions:

- i. Do you have business in your family and have you taken the entrepreneurial education?
- ii. What is your business intention?
- iii. Is there a relationship between family business background, entrepreneurial education, and business intention?

Assumption of the Study

The study assumes that family business background and entrepreneurial education affect the business intention of the students and it can be measured. Further, it also assumes that students answered the questionnaires reflecting the true state of their minds.

The hypothesis of the Study

Early family business exposure and entrepreneurial education help students develop skills, ideas about business, and how to operate a business (Zaman, et.al. 2020). Based on this concept, the current study hypothesizes that there is a correlation between family business, entrepreneurial education, and business intention of the students of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region, Philippines.

Scope and Delimitations of the Study

The scope of the study is the students of the Divine word Colleges in the Ilocos Region, particularly the fourth-year students. It limits its investigation on the family business, entrepreneurial education, and business intention.

Research and Methodology

The research methodology is a scientific process of inquiry. It reflects how the study went through in identifying, selecting, processing, and analyzing information about a topic (Wilkinson, 2000, Leedy, 1974). This is a must-follow procedure to be called scientific and for the study to be valid. The study follows the rule of procedures in the investigation by determining the research design, data gathering instruments method, the population of the study, the locale of the study, the data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design of the study

The study applied a frequency count, descriptive assessment, and correlational research design to determine the number of students who have a family business background, and have taken entrepreneurial education, and to determine the level of the business intention and its correlation. Ariola (2006) contended that a descriptive correlation study is intended to describe the relationship among variables without seeking to establish a causal connection. While descriptive research is simply to describe a population, a situation, or a phenomenon. It is also used to describe profiles, frequency distribution, describe characteristics of people, situations, or phenomena. In short, it answers the question of what, when, how, where, and not why question (McCombes, 2020).

The locale of the Study

The locale of the study was Divine Word College of Laoag in Ilocos Norte.

Population

The respondents of the study are fourth-year students of the Divine Word College of Laoag in Ilocos Norte. Since the number of the students is limited, therefore, the total enumeration sampling was used and thus all fourth-year students were taken as respondents of the study.

Data Gathering instruments

The data were gathered through research questionnaires. The study adapted validated questionnaires of Abun, et.al. (2018) in entrepreneurial attitude and entrepreneurial intention.

Data Gathering Procedures

The integrity and quality of research do not depend only on the content but also depends on the process of how the study is carried out. It has to be done through the right process. Concerning this study, before the researcher distributes the questionnaires, a letter was sent to the President of the college to request him to allow the researcher to float his questionnaires in his respective institutions. In the process of collecting the data, the researcher requests employees’ representatives to retrieve the data from different individual employees before they are submitted to the researcher.

Ethical Procedures

The study was carried out after the research ethics committee examined and approved the procedures and content of the paper if it does not violate ethical standards and if it does not cause harm to human life and the environment.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To analyze the data, descriptive and inferential statistic was used. The frequency count was used to determine the number of students who have a family business and have taken entrepreneurial education and without both. While the weighted mean was used to determine the level of the business intention of the students and the Chi-Square was used to measure the correlation between family business background, entrepreneurship education and business intention of students.

The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation will be used:

<i>Statistical Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
4.21-5.00	strongly agree/Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree/High
2.61-3.40	somewhat agree/moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree/Low
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree/Very Low

Empirical Data and Analysis

This part presents the data that was gathered through the research questionnaires. The presentation follows the statement of the problem of the study. The results are presented in the table form.

Problem1: Do you have business in your family and have you taken entrepreneurial education?

Table 1: Distribution of the respondents as to whether they have a family business, and if they have taken an entrepreneurial education (n=279)

Factors	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Presence of family business		
Yes	125	44.80
No	154	55.20
Have taken entrepreneurial education		
Yes	178	63.80
No	101	36.20

Based on the data presented in the table, shows that 125 out of 279 students or 44.80 % of the fourth-year students have a family business background and 154 out 279 students have no family business background or 55.20% of the fourth-year students have no family business background. It indicates that the majority of fourth-year students have no family business background.

In terms of entrepreneurial education, the data reveals that 178 out of 279 students or 63.80 % of students have taken their entrepreneurial education. While 101 out of 279 or 36.20% of students have not taken entrepreneurial education. It appears that the majority of students have taken entrepreneurial education.

Problem2: What is your business intention?

Table 2: Business intentions of the respondents

Business intentions indicators	Weighted mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. My professional goal is to become an entrepreneur.	3.56	Agree/High
2. I will make every effort to start and run my own business.	3.87	Agree/High
3. I am determined to establish a business in the future.	3.90	Agree/High
4. I am seriously considering putting up a business in the future.	3.94	Agree/High
5. I have the firm intention to start a firm someday	3.60	Agree/High
6. I am ready to do anything to be an entrepreneur	3.58	Agree/High
7. If I will open a business I have a chance to become successful.	3.88	Agree/High
8. Being an entrepreneur would make me great	3.73	Agree/High
9. I have ideas about how to start a business in the future	3.53	Agree/High
10. It will not be difficult for me to develop business ideas	3.42	Agree/High
Overall mean	3.70	High

As gleaned from the data on the table, it reveals that the overall mean rating of the business intention of the fourth-year students of the Divine Word College of Laoag is 3.70 which is interpreted as "agree or high". This mean rating suggests that the business intention of the fourth-year students are not very high and it is not also low or very low but it is high. Even if the indicators are taken separately, all are rated within the same mean range level with the interpretation of "agree or high". The students highly agree that their personal goal is to become an entrepreneur and start their businesses in the future. They also highly agree that they have the idea to run a business and agree that becoming an entrepreneur would make them great.

Problem 3: Is there a relationship between family business background, entrepreneurial education, and business intention?

Table 3: Relationship between Having a Family Business and Business Intentions

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	28.368 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	29.502	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	21.413	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	279		
a. 2 cells (20.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.81.			
Symmetric Measures			
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	Value	Approx. Sig.
	Cramer's V	.319	.000
N of Valid Cases		279	
a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.			
b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.			

The data were analyzed using a Chi-Square Test of Independence (Two Way Chi-Square Test) to determine whether there is a relationship between having a family business and the business intentions of the respondents.

A Chi-Square value of 28.368 (df=4, N=279), $p < .01$, phi coefficient =.319 was obtained which indicates that having a family business and business intentions of the respondents are significantly related. This result suggests that those who have a family business have higher business intentions compared to those who do not have a family business.

Table 4: Relationship between Having Entrepreneurship Education and Business Intention**Chi-Square Tests**

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	36.881 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	36.554	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	30.310	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	279		

a. 2 cells (20.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.79.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.364	.000
	Cramer's V	.364	.000
N of Valid Cases		279	

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

The Chi-Square Test is done to determine the relationship between having an entrepreneurship education and business intention of the respondents resulted in a Chi-Square value of 36.881 (df=4, N=279), $p < .01$, phi coefficient = .364.

This result indicates that the entrepreneurship education background of the respondents is significantly related to their business intentions. This finding suggests that those who have an entrepreneurship education background have higher business intentions compared to those who do not have an entrepreneurship background.

Results and Discussions

Based on the result of the Chi-Square test, it indicates that family business background and entrepreneurial education background make a difference to the business intention of the students. Such results suggest that students who have a family business and who have taken entrepreneurship education influence them more to become an entrepreneur in the future compared to those who have no family business background and entrepreneurship education background. This result points out that business intention is a result of exposure to the family business and a result of entrepreneurship education that they have taken. Exposure to family business gives the students real experience on what business is and how to run a business. This result confirms the previous finding of Wang, et.al. (2018) about the effect of the family business on the business intention of the children. The education has given them the idea or knowledge of what business is all about and how to run it. As Batanero, et al. (2016) as cited by Lv, et al. (2021) argued that having entrepreneurial knowledge, skills and spirit can affect the business intention.

The results recommend to the curriculum designer to consider giving more opportunities to students who have no family business background to be exposed to different businesses. Having real experience in the business would inspire them more to become an entrepreneur. Observing people in the business, particularly how a business is managed will give them the skills and eventually motivate students to become an entrepreneur. It is also true that encountering great business entrepreneurs would change their perception about the image of an entrepreneur as Taraquez (2016) pointed out a positive image of an entrepreneur would motivate students to become an entrepreneur.

A further finding of the study indicates that students who have no family background and have no entrepreneurship education background have lower business intentions compared to those who have both. The finding suggests that entrepreneurship education must be offered to all students and exposure to different business industries according to different specializations must be provided to all students. It is a fact that not all who are in the business are graduates of business education and those who have a family business background but many of them come from a different educational background and even without formal education or a degree (Toren, 2011).

Conclusion

The study aimed to determine the effect of family business background, entrepreneurial education background on the business intention of the students of the Divine Word College of Laoag. The study found that 125 out of 279 students have a family business background and 154 out of 279 have no family business background. In terms of entrepreneurial education background, the majority or 178 (63.80%) out of 279 students have taken entrepreneurial education and 101 out of 279 or 36.20 % have not taken their entrepreneurial education.

Concerning their business intention, the result indicates that the students' overall mean rating of 3.70 which is high. This suggests that they have a high business intention and plan to go into business once they graduate from college.

In terms of the correlation between family business, entrepreneurial education background and business intention, the result Chi-Square test indicates that there is a significant correlation. Students who have a family background and entrepreneurial education background have higher business intention compared to those who have no both.

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